

Reactions of B. Ed. Student-Teachers towards Feedback System Adopted By the Department of Education of The M. S. University Of Baroda

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Abstract

Practice teaching or a student teaching is a process through which a student-teacher secures guided experiences as a preparation for all aspects of his professional career. The process of feedback is an important dimension in practice teaching. The main function of giving feedback is to provide data about the individual's teaching study, teaching skills, different acts of behaviours and its effect on others. Through the feedback, the student-teachers can know their positive and negative areas observed in their practicing lessons and thereby improving their practice lessons. Therefore, keeping in mind the importance of feedback in practice teaching, the authors of this paper attempted to study the reactions of student-teachers about the feedback system adopted by the Department of Education (CASE), The M. S. University of Baroda. All 180 student-teachers enrolled during the year 2011-12 were constituted as a sample and a constructed reaction scale was implemented. This paper highlights the major findings, its discussion and implications for the teacher training.

KEYWORDS: Feedback, Practice teaching, Reactions, Student-teachers

INTRODUCTION

Practice teaching or student teaching is a process through which a student teacher secures guided experiences as a preparation for all aspects of his professional career. Generally, a student teaching programme is organized to expose the student teacher to a variety of teaching-learning situations so that he may develop into an effective classroom teacher according to his capacity and zeal. Other purposes of student teaching is to acquaint him/her with different techniques and approaches related to teaching methods, materials, communication behaviours in the classroom, and also to develop competence in the basic teaching skills (Pandey & Khosla, 1979).

The practice teaching programme at Department of Education is organized in the manner that takes care of most of the objectives given by NCERT (1974) and Sharma (1999). An attempt is made to provide a large variety of learning experiences to the student teachers.

The effective supervisory feedback would go a long way in accomplishing most of them. The process of feedback is an important dimension in practice teaching. In a practice teaching situation, the supervisor interacts with the student teachers, communicates how the latter has been doing or where he has not fared well, or how things can be improved. Such interactions can be the basis of teaching effectiveness. The role of the supervisors is to help the student teachers to improve their own teaching (Brown, 1975). Feedback refers to those acts of the supervisor which tell the student teacher whether they are progressing in the right direction or not. If better solutions are evolved as a result of feedback, and if student teachers implement these

with earnestness, it may contribute both to their teaching effectiveness and the effectiveness of the school organization as a whole.

In a practice teaching situation, supervisor needs to communicate his feelings, impressions and views on various matters. When such feelings and perceptions are communicated to the student teachers, regarding his behavior, style of teaching etc. it is called as feedback. The supervisor shares his perceptions about the students' achievements, strengths as well as the areas in which there is scope of improvement.

The main function of giving feedback is to provide data about the individuals teaching style, teaching skills, different acts of behaviours and its effect on others. Such data can be verified by the individual by either collecting more data from the other sources for example the peer group. The feedback also provides several alternatives to the individuals out of which he can choose the best option to act upon.

Feedback in the practice teaching helps the student-teachers in knowing their positive and negative areas observed in their practicing lessons and thereby improving their practice lessons. The feedback is important in practice teaching programme as it is integral to formative assessment, produces learner autonomy, aligns teaching and learning and it directly impacts student experience.

Reaction towards feedback can be defined as the sum total of the B. Ed. student-teachers' inclination, feeling, prejudice and bias, ideas and conviction about a particular aspect/s related to the feedback. By this definition the scope of the perception study is limited to B. Ed. student-teachers' reaction with regard to special objects and events related to the feedback.

Realizing the importance of reaction as a construct, the investigators were interested in studying the reactions of B. Ed. student-teachers who are undergoing with the system and their reactions will decide whether in future as part of the practice teaching, would they like to continue with the present feedback system or make appropriate changes in the feedback system.

In teacher preparation programme, it is mostly responsibility of the training college supervisors, practicing school teachers and the peer group to provide information to a student-teacher about his/her teaching behavior which is rich enough and clear enough to enable him/her to compare his/her performance with his/her own intentions. The success of teacher education programme depends most of all, on the quality of guidance provided to the student-teachers and soundness of the supervision programme in helping him/her.

Flanders (1964) viewed that the lack of feedback has plagued teacher training for centuries. Interaction analysis, if learned by student-teachers, would be valuable tool for helping them view their own behavior in student-teaching more objectively and help them find out relationship between their intentions, goals and behavior.

GCPI (1979), Mishra (1983) and Paikaray (1981) compared different feedback methods for changing teacher-behaviour, effect of micro-teaching under varying sources of feedback and different types of feedback in micro-teaching respectively while Misra (1985) measured effect of self-rating and class-rating feedback on

teachers' classroom behaviour. All the studies found on feedback were experimental studies and measured effectiveness of various sources of feedback. Only a study of Paikaray (1981) measured reaction of teacher trainees towards feedback for the micro-teaching but no single researcher have measured reaction or reaction of student-teachers towards the feedback provided by the different sources to them.

The Department of Education (CASE) of the M. S. University of Baroda offers one year full time B. Ed. course wherein 180 students from Arts, Commerce and Science streams are admitted on the basis of merit. The practice teaching programme of the CASE provides opportunities to practice the essential skills and other attributes needed to become an effective teacher who can cater to the ever-changing needs and demands of the society. The programme is organized in a manner that takes care of most of the objectives of NCERT (1974) and Sharma (1999). An attempt is made to provide a large variety of learning experiences to the student teachers (Patel & Mehta, 2003). Therefore, keeping these in mind all these, the investigator thought to conduct a study on the feedback about the practice teaching by constructing the reaction scale for the B.Ed. student-teachers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- ❑ To construct the scale to measure reactions towards feedback system.
- ❑ To measure the reactions of B. Ed. student-teachers of the M. S. University of Baroda towards feedback system.

EXPLANATION OF THE TERM USED

Feedback system: It is a feedback provided to the B. Ed. student-teachers during their practice teaching lessons in the real classroom settings where the supervisor and other B. Ed. student-teachers provides their positive or negative opinions on the classroom teaching-learning process, skills used, participation and involvement of students, classroom management, content mastery, activities carried out and regarding the whole lesson given by the student-teacher in practicing school.

OPERATIONALIZATION OF THE TERM USED

Reaction towards Feedback: It is the perception, thinking and feeling of B. Ed. student-teachers towards feedback which was measured with the help of five point scale consisting of content area, skills of teaching, pedagogy of teaching, and way of giving feedback aspects. The reaction were measured from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The total score reflects the reaction of the B. Ed. student-teachers of the M. S. University of Baroda towards feedback system.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Research Design

The present study was descriptive study where the investigators attempted to find out the reality.

Population

All the B. Ed. student-teachers of the Department of Education (CASE), the M. S. University of Baroda were constituted the population for the present study. There are 180 seats available in B. Ed. course. So, all the 180 student-teachers of the B. Ed. programme during the academic year 2011-2012 comprised population for the present study.

Sample

Since the problem under study is mainly confined to the B. Ed. student-teachers of the Department of Education (CAES), the M. S. University of Baroda only and the population i.e. 180 B. Ed. student-teachers being small, the entire population of the B. Ed. student-teachers was taken for the sample. However, 15 B. Ed. student-teachers who have left the course were omitted and 165 registered student-teachers for the year 2011-12 were selected as a sample for the present study. But, out of 165 B. Ed. student-teachers, 19 B. Ed. student-teachers were absent during the time of data collection, so the data were collected from 144 B. Ed. student-teachers. Thus, the size of the sample remained to 144 B. Ed. student-teachers of the Department of Education (CASE), the M. S. University of Baroda.

Tools

To measure the reactions of the B. Ed. student-teachers towards feedback, a five-point Likert type *Reaction Scale* was constructed by the investigators. The scale was constructed after reviewing materials regarding the practice teaching and a number of scales constructed earlier. Based on the formal discussion with the experts in the field and review of materials related to feedback, the investigators identified 4 dimensions viz., impact of feedback, effect of feedback on practicing lessons, role of feedback giver and limitations of the feedback. 50 items were constructed and the initial draft was referred to the experts in the field. Based on the suggestions of experts, necessary modifications were done and final scale was constructed.

Face validity was ensured by referring the scale to the experts in the field. The reliability of the constructed reaction scale was determined by the split-half method. This method was chosen as it is neither desirable nor feasible for the investigators to administer the same reaction scale, two times for 'Test-Retest reliability'. The correlation coefficient of two halves was found to be .475. The reliability of the reaction scale was found to be .676 by Guttman Split-half method and .677 by equal length. Spearman Brown formula, indicating high reliability of the scale in terms of consistency among the items in the single administration of the tool on the pre-service B.Ed. student teachers of the Department of Education (CASE) of the M. S. University of Baroda.

Along with the reaction scale, five open-ended questions were also asked in terms of to get additional responses regarding their opinions about feedback, problems and suggestions for improvement (if any) from the B. Ed. student-teachers.

DATA COLLECTION

The investigator had visited to Head of the Department of Education (CASE), the M. S. University and submitted the forward letter depicting the purpose of the study and its importance. After getting the permission from the Head of the Department, decided the time schedule to collect the data from the B. Ed. student-teachers of the Department of Education (CASE). After that, the investigator had collected the data from the B. Ed. student-teachers of the Department of Education (CASE), the M. S. University of Baroda on 30th January, 2012.

DATA ANALYSIS

The collected data were analyzed both quantitatively as well as qualitatively. Frequency, percentage and intensity index were counted based on the responses of the B. Ed. student-teachers in terms to study their reactions towards the feedback about

the practice teaching. The subjective answers of the respondents supporting their choice were qualitatively analyzed. Content analysis was done for the open ended questions.

MAJOR FINDINGS

- ❑ Out of the total 144 respondent student teachers, sixty six (45.83 percent) student teachers agreed to the item that 'I don't like critical feedback during practicing lessons'. The intensity index of 2.97 showed undecided reaction of student teachers towards their liking or disliking of the critical feedback.
- ❑ Sixty seven (46.52 percent) student teachers disagreed to the item 'Critical feedback during practicing lessons lowers my self-esteem'. The intensity index 2.66 showed undecided reaction of the student teachers towards the affection of critical feedback on their self-esteem.
- ❑ Majority of the student teachers i.e. 122 (84.72 percent) student teachers agreed to the item 'Supervisor gives critical feedback safely for further improvement'. The intensity index 4.09 showed agreed reaction of student teachers towards the item.
- ❑ Most of them i.e. 132 (91.66 percent) student teachers agreed to the item 'Supervisor gives feedback likely to be helpful to me'. The intensity index 4.39 showed agreed reaction of the student teachers towards the item.
- ❑ Eighty seven (60.41 percent) agreed to the item 'Feedback provided by the supervisor creates negative reaction'. The intensity index 2.36 showed that the student teachers were agreed to the item.
- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 101 (70.13) student teachers agreed to the item 'Supervisor gives critical feedback with real feeling and trust'. The intensity index 3.50 showed that the student teachers agreed with the item.
- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 104 (72.22 percent) student teachers agreed to the item 'I can trust the supervisor whenever s/he gives critical feedback'. The intensity index 3.69 showed agreed reaction of the student teachers towards the item.
- ❑ Ninety six (66.66 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement 'Supervisor devotes enough time for giving feedback'. The intensity index 3.50 showed agreed reaction of student teachers for the item.
- ❑ Most of them i.e. 122 (84.72 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement 'Supervisor gives feedback regularly'. The intensity index 4.09 showed agreed reaction of student teachers for the item.
- ❑ Most of them i.e. 121 (84.02) student teachers agreed to the statement 'Feedback is meaningful for becoming an effective teacher'. The intensity index 4.20 showed agreed reactions of the student teachers towards the item.
- ❑ 100 (69.44 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement 'Supervisor does not describe everything about the situation while giving feedback'. The intensity index 3.65 showed they disagreed with the item.
- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 109 (75.69 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement 'Supervisor provides evaluative judgment in feedback'. The intensity index 3.73 showed agreed reaction of the student teachers towards the item.
- ❑ Eighty five (59.02 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement 'Supervisor provides descriptive feedback'. The intensity index 3.5 showed that they agreed to the item.
- ❑ Most of them i.e. 120 (83.33 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement 'I cannot decide better about my behaviour after receiving feedback'. The

intensity index 4.06 showed the disagreed reaction of the student teachers to the item.

- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 114 (79.16 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement 'Specific feedback helps to recall the exact instance'. The intensity index 3.95 showed that they agreed to the item.
- ❑ 102 (70.83 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement 'Supervisor reinforces positive behaviour first'. The intensity index 3.81 showed their agreed reaction towards the item.
- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 102 (70.83 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement 'Feedback does not provide remedial measures'. The intensity index 3.83 showed that they were disagreed towards the item.
- ❑ Most of them i.e. 119 (82.63 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement 'Feedback does not help in bringing positive change in behaviour'. The intensity index 4.08 showed their disagreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Most of them i.e. 123 (85.41 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement 'Feedback does not help in the improvement of performance'. The intensity index 4.24 showed the disagreed reaction of the student teachers towards the item.
- ❑ Forty nine (34.02 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement 'Supervisor tells shortcomings that don't have control' whereas, thirty two (22.22 percent) student teachers agreed. The intensity index 3.06 showed their undecided reaction for the item.
- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 105 (72.91 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement 'Feedback helps in avoiding ineffective behaviour'. The intensity index 3.75 showed their agreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Ninety two (63.88 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement 'Supervisor suggests different alternatives in critical events'. The intensity index 3.51 showed their agreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Ninety six (66.66 percent) student teachers disagreed to the item 'Supervisor does not give feedback politely'. The intensity index of 3.61 showed disagreed reaction of student teachers towards the item.
- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 106 (73.61 percent) student teachers agreed to the item 'Supervisor helps me to face weak points in a frank and objective manner'. The intensity index 3.86 showed agreed reaction of the student teachers towards the item.
- ❑ Sixty seven (46.52 percent) student teachers disagreed to the item 'Supervisor discriminates and favours while giving feedback' whereas, thirty nine (27.08 percent) student teachers agreed. The intensity index 2.62 showed undecided reaction towards the item.
- ❑ Sixty nine (47.91 percent) student teachers disagreed to the item 'Feedback becomes ineffective due to supervisor's lack of fluency in language' whereas, fifty (34.72 percent) agreed. The intensity index 2.76 showed undecided agreed reaction of the student teachers towards the item.
- ❑ Fifty six (38.88 percent) disagreed to the item 'Communication during feedback makes confusion due to muddles thoughts of supervisors' whereas, fifty eight (40.27 percent) agreed to the item. The intensity index 2.93 showed that the student teachers were undecided to the item.
- ❑ Eighty four (58.33 percent) student teachers agreed to the item 'Supervisor always checks about my receiving and understanding of feedback'. The intensity index 3.52 showed that the student teachers agreed to the item.

- ❑ Fifty nine (40.97 percent) student teachers agreed to the item ‘Supervisor presents feedback as per the others opinion’ whereas, fifty five (38.19 percent) student teachers disagreed. The intensity index 2.90 showed undecided reaction of the student teachers towards the item.
- ❑ Sixty four (44.44 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Supervisor provides very global feedback’ whereas, forty one (28.47 percent) of the disagreed. The intensity index 3.20 showed their undecided reaction for the item.
- ❑ Forty eight (33.33 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement ‘Feedback given is more on pedagogy than content’ whereas, fifty eight (40.27 percent) of them agreed. The intensity index 3.02 showed undecided reaction of student teachers for the item.
- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 108 (75 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Feedback related to content will help me improving the transactions’. The intensity index 3.79 showed their agreed reaction towards the item.
- ❑ Eighty eight (61.11 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Feedback is more on teaching skills only’. The intensity index 3.50 showed they agreed to the item.
- ❑ Forty eight (33.33 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement ‘Feedback related to the subject content is very rare’ whereas, sixty (41.66 percent) of them agreed. The intensity index 3.06 showed their undecided reaction for the item.
- ❑ Fifty (34.72 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement ‘Grading in practice lessons is not very objective’ whereas, sixty one (42.36 percent) of them agreed. The intensity index 3.12 showed that they were undecided to the item.
- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 105 (72.91 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement ‘Grading is affected if examiners are different’. The intensity index 3.81 showed their disagreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Sixty four (44.44 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement ‘Grading is based on favoritism and not the actual performance’ whereas, forty one (28.47 percent) student teachers agreed. The intensity index 2.63 showed that they were undecided towards the item.
- ❑ Ninety nine (63.19 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Feedback given will be more objective if my method master evaluates my lesson’. The intensity index 3.77 showed their agreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Eighty seven (60.41 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Supervisor observes only few of the lessons and grades without observing other things’ whereas, thirty eight (26.38 percent) student teachers disagreed. The intensity index 2.39 showed their agreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Sixty five (45.13 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement ‘Supervisor does not devote more time in observing whole lesson’ whereas, forty nine (34.02 percent) student teachers agreed. The intensity index 2.72 showed their undecided reaction for the item.
- ❑ Sixty nine (47.91 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement ‘I am not much satisfied with the way feedback is provided’ whereas, fifty three (36.80 percent) student teachers agreed. The intensity index 2.79 showed the undecided reaction for the item.
- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 112 (77.77 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Feedback is provided everyday’. The intensity index 3.97 showed agreed reaction for the item.

- ❑ Eighty nine (61.79 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Supervisor clearly specifies the limitations’. The intensity index 3.61 showed their agreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 108 (75 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Supervisor appreciates my strengths’. The intensity index 3.86 showed their agreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Majority of them i.e. 105 (72.91 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Supervisor appreciate in presence of all group members’. The intensity index 3.67 showed their agreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Ninety two (63.88 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Supervisor talks about my weaknesses in front of all group members’. The intensity index 3.5 showed the agreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Sixty five (45.13 percent) student teachers disagreed to the statement ‘Supervisor is very harsh in providing feedback’ whereas, forty four (30.55 percent) student teachers agreed. The intensity index 2.63 showed undecided reaction for the item.
- ❑ Eighty two (56.94 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Feedback provided by my peers are very rationale’. The intensity index 3.50 showed their agreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Most of them i.e. 121 (84.02 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Feedback improves my practicing lessons’. The intensity index 4.25 showed their agreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ Seventy six (52.77 percent) student teachers agreed to the statement ‘Written feedback is more effective then verbal feedback’. The intensity index 3.50 showed their agreed reaction for the item.
- ❑ 112 student teachers were satisfied with the feedback provided to them by their supervisor whereas, twenty two of the student teachers were not satisfied with the feedback provided to them due to negative feedback, harsh and critical feedback and irregularity of feedback.
- ❑ Majority of the student teachers (eighty four) opined that the feedback made them aware about their strength and their weaknesses which in turn helped them as to how to reduce their weakness and also motivated them to strengthen their strengths.
- ❑ 132 of the student-teachers responded that the feedback affecting positively in their practicing lessons in giving good lessons, knowing strength & weakness, boosting self-confidence, improving overall lesson, and correcting oneself.
- ❑ The improvements suggested by thirty eight student teachers are un-biased feedback, performance based feedback, uniformity in the feedback, positive feedback, keen observation of the lessons before giving feedback, more objectivity and reduce subjectivity in feedback, suggestions of alternative solution for improvement of lessons, more focus on the subject and the content matter along with the skills of teaching.
- ❑ Majority of the student teachers suggested for regularity in providing feedback. The other suggestions received from the student teachers were, supervisors should focus on the most important part of teaching, politeness in providing feedback, observation of entire class, regularity in feedback and supervisor should be respective method master and individual feedback.

DISCUSSION

Feedback in practice teaching is powerful as it helps student teachers get on right track of the practicing lessons. It also serves as a guide to assist student teachers to

know how they and others perceive their performance. Feedback can also be very motivating and energizing. Practicing lessons without feedback is similar to setting out an important journey minus a map or signposts. It is very difficult to know the performance in practice lessons and thereby progress without feedback from the supervisors and peers as feedback from others informs student teachers in ways that enriches their self knowledge for the practice lessons, teaching and skills and appropriate behaviour in classroom. Feedback in the practice teaching can lead in improvement of practicing lessons by knowing the positive as well as negative areas from the observation of the lessons. The present study was an attempt in the field of reaction measurement of B.Ed. student teachers towards the feedback system adopted by the Department of Education (CASE), The M. S. University of Baroda.

The result of the present study indicates that the majority of the respondent student teachers of the Department of Education (CASE), The M. S. University of Baroda were reacted positively to the feedback system adopted by the Department of Education (CASE), The M. S. University of Baroda as majority of them were reacted favourably to the items related to critical feedback from supervisor for further improvement and with real feeling & trust, helpfulness of feedback in avoiding ineffective behaviour, regularity in feedback, meaningfulness of feedback for becoming an effective teacher, evaluative judgement from supervisor in feedback, help of specific feedback to recall the exact instance, reinforcement from supervisor for positive behaviour, helps from supervisor to face weak points in a frank & objective manner, affection in grading due to different examiners, appreciation of strengths by supervisors in presence of all group members and improvement in practicing lessons.

The result of the present study further indicates that the feedback system adopted by the Department of Education (CASE), The M. S. University of Baroda, needs to improve in some of the areas as more than thirty percent of the respondent student teachers were reacted that the critical feedback lowering self-esteem, feedback creates negative reaction, supervisors telling short comings that don't have control, discrimination and favour in feedback, feedback becomes ineffective due to supervisor's lack of fluency in language, communication during feedback makes confusion due to muddles thoughts of supervisor, supervisor provides feedback as per others opinions, feedback is more on pedagogy and teaching skills while very rare on subject content, no objectivity in grading and grading is based on favouritism, supervisors observes only few of the lessons and grades without observing other things, supervisor doesn't devote more time in observing whole lesson and being very harsh in providing feedback and they are not satisfied with the way of feedback.

It is also evident that some conceptual confusion seems to persist in the minds of student teachers, as to the place of skills-teaching within methods of teaching. This is noticeable in the manner in which it is carried out. During practice lessons there is great insistence on the use of skills, as if this by itself would make teaching effective. On the other hand, use of different methods is also emphasized. That all instructional methods require these skills differentially and that their use depends on several factors such as the nature of content, learners, facilities and the teacher himself/herself, is not perceived with clarity by the students. During the practice period the student teacher gets an impression that 'displaying' instructional skills in very important to gain the approval of the supervisors rather than using them as tools for implementing a

specific method. Therefore the use of these skills is rather more mechanical and superficial than naturalistic and therefore there is a dire need to bring in the clarity and remove the misconceptions prevailing in the minds of the students. According to NCFTE (2009) practice teaching which constitutes the most functional part of the teacher preparation has suffered severe neglect and dilution in quality. The common complaint is that theory dominates the curriculum and practice teaching continues to suffer from inadequacies of different kinds such as: it follows a mechanical routine, operates with rigid lesson plan formats, inadequate mentoring and supervision; exhibits no original thinking, lacks variety and context specificity in teaching. There is no attempt made towards comprehensive, qualitative evaluation covering professional attitudes and values and provision of sustained engagement with schools. The present study also reveals similar scenario where the feedback provided to the students were not very comprehensive, supervisor not observing entire lesson and not specifying the modification that is to be brought about in the lesson plans.

The creation of negative reactions through the feedback may be due to biasness or unspecific & unclear feedback. The other reason could be lack of observation of whole lesson. The supervisors should not give feedback that discourages the student teachers or threatens their self esteem. Feedback should be focused on the specific features of the task i.e. practicing lessons given by the student teachers not student teachers. Too controlling or critical feedback also can lead the negative reactions of the student teachers. Supervisors should be specific and clear with the feedback messages and also should provide elaborated to enhance the performance of the student teachers. The feedback in description form along with where improvement needed, how it can be improved, what options are there for improvement etc will benefit to the student teachers for improving their performance then mere verification of performance of the student teachers.

Majority of the student teachers were satisfied with the feedback provided to them by their supervisor and the student teachers who were not satisfied with the feedback provided due to negative feedback, harsh and critical feedback and irregularity of feedback. Regarding the helps from the feedback in improving practicing lessons, the student teachers opined that the feedback made them aware about their strength and their weaknesses which in turn helped them as to how to reduce their weakness and also motivated them to strengthen their strengths in giving lessons. With regard to the affection of feedback in practicing lessons, most of the student teachers responded that the feedback affecting positively in their practicing lessons in giving good lessons, knowing strength and weakness, boosting self confidence, improving overall lesson and correcting oneself. For the scope of improvement in feedback system, the suggestions received by student teachers were un-biased feedback, performance based feedback, uniformity in the feedback, positive feedback, keen observation of the lessons before giving feedback, more objectivity and reduce subjectivity in feedback, suggestions of alternative solution for improvement of lessons, more focus on the subject and the content matter along with the skills of teaching. Majority of the student teachers also suggested for regularity in providing feedback. The other suggestions received from the student teachers were, supervisors should focus on the most important part of teaching, politeness in providing feedback, observation of entire class, regularity in feedback and supervisor should be respective method master and individual feedback.

The idealistic logic with which the teacher educator is sent to observe the lessons transacted by the student teacher is that a teacher educator is a technical expert who, with field experience and theoretical understanding of teaching and related processes, will be able to discern the strengths and weaknesses of a student teacher at every stage of the teaching-learning process, suggest more effective alternatives and provide theoretical explanations for the ways different teaching events occur. Such a technical and sensitive handling of the situation would not only make a student teacher recognize what works or what does not work in his/her instructional design and the theoretical explanation for it, but also gain insight into the process of selecting alternatives. This insight is crucial for teaching effectiveness. But the scenario is that teacher educator with one specialization is required to observe the student teachers with a varied specializations. There is a dire need to have a strong collaboration of teacher education institution with the practicing schools and attaching the subject teachers with the student teacher so that the subject teacher play the role of mentors to the student teacher and take care of the student teachers by providing the technical and moral support to the student teacher so as to bring within each one of the student teacher the knowhow of what works or what does not work in his/her instructional design.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The present study has found on what need to be done to improve feedback system in terms to make it more effective.

- ❑ To increase the objectivity in the observations of lessons and thereby providing feedback, the research suggest observation of the lessons by the method master.
- ❑ As the supervisors have to provide feedback to group of 8-10 student teachers in same time, use of immediate and delay feedback will be useful to both supervisors and student teachers. The supervisors can use immediate feedback for difficult tasks which will helpful to student teachers to cope up with the difficult tasks and they will not be frustrated. The immediate feedback will more benefit in the case of low achieving student teachers. Same as, the supervisors can use delayed feedback for relatively simple tasks which in turn will promote transfer of learning. This kind of feedback can be benefit in the case of high achieving student teachers.

CONCLUSION

It is obvious that in imparting professional rigour to the preparation of a teacher, the practice of teaching and associated rigorous theoretical study play a crucial part. It is the effectiveness with which the multiple components of field learning—getting to know the school, observing children, observing teaching and learning in real classroom contexts, practicing teaching, developing capacities to think with educational theories and applying concepts in concrete teaching-learning situations, managing classroom learning, evaluating learners and providing feedback, learning to work with colleagues, reflecting on one's own professional practice—are drawn upon to provide appropriate learning experiences for the student teacher that is critical to the education of teachers. At the outset, it can be seen that any attempt towards reform of current practices and design of innovative approaches in practice teaching should begin with an understanding of the place of teaching practice in the overall scheme of things. The first thing to be noted is that the practice of teaching constitutes the hub of the multiple and varied activities comprising the total programme of teacher education. It is interconnected with theoretical study, field work and practicum and a

wide range of institutional experiences involving school students, teachers, student teachers, mentor teacher educators. There needs to be a proper collaboration of teacher education institutions and practicing schools to make the students get real feel of school apart from teaching as an isolated components.

REFERENCES

- Brown, G. (1975). *Microteaching: A Programme of Teaching Skills*, London: Methuen & Co Ltd.
- GCPI (1979). *A Comparative study of Effects of Microteaching under Varying Sources of Feedback and Attitudes of Teacher-trainees towards Teaching*. An Unpublished Doctoral Thesis (Education), Allahabad University. Uttar Pradesh: Allahabad.
- NCTE (2009). *National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education*, New Delhi: NCTE.
- Paikaray, G.S. (1981). A Comparison of Different Types of Feedback in Microteaching upon Teaching Competence and attitude towards Teaching of Student-teachers. In M.B. Buch (Ed.). *Third Survey of Research in Education*, Baroda : Society for Educational Research and Development (1978-83). p. 258.
- Pandey, B. N. & Khosla, D. N. (1974). *Student Teaching & Evaluation: A Handbook of Secondary Colleges of Education*, New Delhi: NCERT.
- Patel, R. C. & Mehta, A. (2003). Practice Teaching at CASE. In *Policies and Issues in Teacher Education*. Pp. 50-54. Baroda: CASE.
- Sharma, R. A. (1999). *Teacher Education*. Meerut: Loyal Book Depot.